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Research Article

EFFECT OF LIFESTYLE INTERVENTIONS ON DIABETIC PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES.¹Dr Bakhtawar Huma Khan, ²Dr Misbah Nawaz, ³Dr Hamna Ifthihar Niazi¹MBBS, Fatima Jinnah Medical College, Lahore.²MBBS, Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore.³WMO, Friends Welfare Trust Hospital.**Article Received:** December 2019 **Accepted:** January 2020 **Published:** February 2020**Abstract:**

The aim of this study was to discover the effect of lifestyle interventions on the severity of diabetic peripheral neuropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes. The prevalence of diabetic neuropathy is approximately 60% which is the most common form of neuropathy in the developed countries. Almost half of all the patients with diabetes mellitus are suffering from neuropathy. Coming up with considerable mortality and morbidity and has a high burden on economic. Results of the study has shown that regardless of high levels of neuropathic disorder among diabetic patients, using safe and effective methods such as lifestyle modification can help in lowering the severity of diabetic peripheral neuropathy and increases the comfort among such patients. Current study has strong evidence of lifestyle modification will successfully reduce the severity of peripheral neuropathy among the patients of diabetic peripheral neuropathy

Corresponding author:**Dr. Bakhtawar Huma Khan,**
MBBS, Fatima Jinnah Medical College, Lahore.

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INTRODUCTION:

Of the 21st century diabetes mellitus is one of the major public health emergencies World widely. Approximately 415 million adults have DM and by 2040 this number will rise to 642 million [1]. The prevalence of diabetic neuropathy is approximately 60% which is the most common form of neuropathy in the developed countries. Almost half of all the patients with diabetes mellitus are suffering from neuropathy. Coming up with considerable mortality and morbidity and has a high burden on economic. Diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) is the most common form which usually targets the lower limb and causes morbidity due to the consequences of subsequent ulcers, amputation and disability [2] [3] [4] Diabetic neuropathy severely disturbs the individual's quality of life and control of diabetes moreover it worsens the prognosis of other diabetic related complications [5]. Diabetic neuropathy has been known by the presence of at least two following characteristics: (1) Pain, paresthesia or numbness; (2) zero tendon reflex; (3) abnormal perception threshold. [6]. Literature has reported that good glycemic control have better prognosis of nerve function in diabetic patients [7] [8]. However many studies have strongly suggest that sever glycemic control can lower the risk of getting diabetic neuropathy in type 1 diabetic patients and it may decreases the risk in patients suffering from type 2 diabetes. [9] [10][11]. Continuous unhealthy choice of diet, smoking, alcohol, sedentary life style compromises in up to 40% premature deaths in United States. On the other hand healthy and active life style, comfortable environment and pleasurable behaviors are prone toward high expectancy of life as compared people suffering from diabetic neuropathy [12].

The aim of this study was to discover the effect of lifestyle interventions on the severity of diabetic peripheral neuropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

It was a randomized clinical trial. Patients who met the eligibility criteria invited to participate. Participants who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Eligibility criteria were Adults aged 18 or more suffering with diabetic neuropathy, without any ulcer on their foot. Patients were excluded if they had known non-diabetic causes of neuropathy (for example, vitamin deficiencies, uremia, thyroid disease, lumbar or cervical radiculopathy, inflammatory neuropathy or presence of alcoholism). The sample size was 80. The p value was ≤ 0.05 with 95% confidence of interval. For measuring the severity of neuropathy, participants were allowed a 10-minute acclimatization period in constant room

temperature ($24 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) after they had removed their socks and shoes. The Toronto Clinical Neuropathy Score (TCNS) is a sensitive scoring system used to diagnose diabetic neuropathy, and to measure changes in such early diabetic sensorimotor polyneuropathy (DSP) pathophysiology. TCNS can be used as an inexpensive bedside screening tool [13,14]. The TCNS was modified (into the mTCNS) to better capture a categorical scale of simple sensory tests, which are better representative of the early dysfunction in DSP, and to eliminate reflex testing, which represent the late-stage pathophysiology of DSP, are highly variable between raters, age dependent and heavily weighted in the TCNS. The mTCNS, a clinical score with higher face validity for tracking mild to moderate DSP, has sufficient reliability and validity relative to its precursor TCNS for use in clinical research [15]. mTCNS consists of graded symptoms (foot pain, numbness, tingling, weakness, ataxia and upper limb symptoms) and a sensory test (pinprick, temperature, light touch, vibration and position sense) score associated with DPN in the judgment of the examiner. The scale varies from 0 (no signs or symptoms) to 33 (maximal symptoms and signs) [16]. Intervention

The lifestyle interventions applied in the intervention group beginning 4 educational sessions on lifestyle that emphasize strategies for; lowering blood sugar, increasing physical activity, promoting weight loss, and feet caring. Each session was lasted for 1.5 hour. Then patients followed for 12 weeks. During this period, they received individualized counseling on mentioned lifestyle interventions. All participants of intervention group received individualized counseling with goals of reducing weight by 7%, increasing weekly exercise to 150 min, and proper daily feet caring. They received dietary counseling based on their preferences individually, too. Participants in the control group received their routine care and education, without any more education or consulting on lifestyle. Diabetic neuropathy symptom severity in both groups measured using Modified Toronto Clinical Neuropathy Score (mTCNS) at the beginning of study and at the end of counseling for 12 weeks.

RESULTS:

The current study has showed that 88% of the participants were in the control group whereas 63% were in the treatment group. Whereas 30% of females were in the control group and 34% were in intervention group.

There were two groups an intervention group and control group. The mean and standard deviation of age in the control group were (46.3 ± 10.8) and in the intervention group, the mean of age were

(50.38±7.9). The results have shown that there was no remarkable difference in the age of the participants between the two groups. ($p=0.25$)

In the control group, the mean and standard deviation of diabetes duration is (14.89±6.4) and in the intervention group, the mean and standard deviation of diabetes duration is (18±4.6) and there was no significant difference in duration of diabetes between the two groups of study ($p=0.07$). A higher proportion of participants in both groups of study were married. Intervention impact measurement Based on the results of independent t-test, the mean of DPN severity was statistically significant before intervention between two groups of study, but considering before and after differences of the mean of DPN severity, there was significantly decrease in DPN severity of intervention group after the lifestyle intervention; the severity of neuropathy decreased; from the severe to moderate, and from moderate level to mild or to absence of neuropathy symptom level. For example, before the intervention, there were 13 participants with moderate neuropathy, that 5 patients had not any neuropathy symptom (absent of neuropathy) and 8 of them had mild neuropathy, after the end of lifestyle intervention. Comparing the severity of DPN in the control group, the severity of neuropathy had not any change or it increased to a higher level of severity after the end of lifestyle intervention. For example, before the intervention, there were 15 participants with mild neuropathy, that DPN severity in 8 of them reached to moderate level and DPN severity in the rest of 7 patients had not any change after the end of lifestyle intervention.

DISCUSSION:

Key contributors in the development and progression of preventable chronic diseases are poor lifestyle choices, such as smoking, poor diet, lack of physical activity and inadequate relief of chronic stress are, including type 2 diabetes mellitus. Many patients are inadequately prepared to either start or maintain these appropriate, healthy changes even though physicians encourage healthy lifestyle to help prevent or manage many chronic medical conditions [18]. This randomized controlled trial study was designed to clarify the effectiveness of Lifestyle Interventions on the severity of diabetic peripheral neuropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes. The findings support that lifestyle interventions with different strategies for lowering blood sugar, increasing physical activity, promoting weight loss, prudent diet, and foot caring will reduce the severity of DPN. A study conducted by Smit *et al* has similar results with this study, which was on lifestyle intervention for diabetic neuropathy that includes diet control and exercise for patients having no control on glycemic level and resulted in improved pain and

re-innervation of nerves. Another study states that for the patients of diabetes and pre-diabetes many strategies like weight loss and exercise are much helpful in avoiding the risk of DPN [19] [20] [21]

Many other studies conducted on health status improvement cardiovascular risk reduction and prevention of diabetes emphasize on lifestyle modification with diet and exercise plus good glycemic control. The current study has also reported decrease in the severity of DPN with lifestyle intervention as compared to control group.

CONCLUSION:

Results of the study has shown that regardless of high levels of neuropathic disorder among diabetic patients, using safe and effective methods such as lifestyle modification can help in lowering the severity of diabetic peripheral neuropathy and increases the comfort among such patients. Current study has strong evidence of lifestyle modification will successfully reduce the severity of peripheral neuropathy among the patients of diabetic peripheral neuropathy.

By reducing the severity of DPN the quality of life would be enhanced despite DPN is a major reason of lower quality of life due to pain, gait instability, risk of fall, ulceration and amputation.

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